

ISic1280

I.Sicily inscription 1280

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140770

1. [— —] Κ [.] Νεμηγίου [— —]
2. [— — —]#⁷ΡΘΩΝΟΣ Ν [— — —]
3. [— — — —] ΜΕΝΟΙΕ#⁷ [— — —]
4. [— — — — —] ΚΑΣ [— — — —]
- 5.

Edition: PHI316193

1. [— — — — —]ψ Νεμηγίου [— — —]
2. [— — — — —] Ὀρθωνος Ν [— — —]
3. [καὶ οἱ ἀλειφό] μενοι (?) Ε Ρ [— — —]
4. [— — — — —]ΚΑΣ [— — — — —]
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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